

Innovative Leadership as Determinant of Enhancing Transformation of Quality Education in Higher Institutions in Mwanza, Tanzania

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Abstract

This study explores Innovative Leadership determinant of enhancing Transformation of Quality Education in Higher institution in Mwanza Tanzania. A wave of speed of transformation in the era of globalization and industrial progression are creating new promotion forces. One research objective was created to respond to the main question: To determine innovative leadership in improving the Quality of Education in higher institutions in Mwanza. Mixed research approach was applied. Convergent parallel research design was adopted. A sample size of 150 participants was drawn from three higher learning institutions, using stratified and random sampling technique. Questionnaire and interview guide was used to collect data from Innovative leadership practices on improving quality education. Validity of the instrument was done by three experts from the department of measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha giving 0.85 correlation coefficient; analysis was done using statistical for Package Social Science (SPSS) version 24. The result revealed that; there were lack of research experienced faculty, heavy teaching load, moonlighting by faculties, and lack of resources such as library facilities, information and communication technology tools and non-well-equipped laboratories. It was recommended that innovative leadership must be planed for positive changes. The leadership roles in university should be innovative and consistent at every level of organization. The government of Tanzania and other stockholders should foster supporting lecturers by motivating them on innovation and transformative leadership.

Keywords: Innovative Leadership, Transformation, Quality Education, Higher Institutions

Introduction

Transformative Leadership in 21st-century higher education is widely viewed as essential for societal development and prosperity (Altbach et al., 2019). This need is particularly pronounced in Africa, where universities encounter significant obstacles such as limited resources, political instability, and brain drain (Altbach, 2007). The World Bank (2020) reports an annual funding gap of about \$1.2 billion in African higher education, while UNESCO reveals that the average African university relies on government funding for only 16% of its operating budget (UNESCO, 2021).

Transformational leadership has emerged to address these societal challenges by inspiring and motivating followers to reach their full potential while encouraging institutional innovation and change (Northouse, 2018). This leadership style involves crafting an inspiring vision, promoting innovation, and fostering a trusting environment among followers (Sahid et al., 2023). According to Bush (2018), transformational leaders not only create compelling visions and set accountable standards but also exhibit confidence and passion that motivates followers to achieve institutional goals (Kiplangat, 2024).

In institutional contexts, innovative leadership identifies necessary changes, formulates relevant strategies, and actively engages stakeholders in the transformation process, ensuring positive societal impact (Mardizal et al., 2023). Such leadership focuses on work among teachers, the use of new technology in teaching, and policy that is responsive to societal demand. It also creates an environment that promotes experimentation, creativity, and lifelong learning. Innovative leadership is the hallmark of the endless drive to innovate in harmony with educational environments (Halimah et al., 2024). Ategwu et al. (2022) suggest that innovative leadership is a results-focused, integrated process under the premise that organizational effectiveness is a matter of good management. If the leader did not exist, the organization would not have direction, consequently leading to confusion and worse despair (Djoko Hartono, 2020). On the other hand, innovative leadership can transform schools into liquid, flexible terrains that are ready to confront the future with confidence. In this context, innovation is integrated into the school's identity and contributes to the ongoing development and progression of the (Halimah et al., 2024). Notably, after decades in higher development, that the shortsightedness of mainstream leadership in the academy has led to frustration, rebellion and tribalism. This supports the notion that a real demand exists for a shift to a contemporary paradigm where creativity and innovativeness are perceived to be significant for enhancing the quality of university education. Ategwu et al. (2023) one of the greatest challenges for higher education, when considering the lack of managerial and administrative competences. They must also face faculty hiring and retention, public perception problems, diversity and inclusivity problems, and corruption and nepotism. Notwithstanding these challenges, global research literature in respect of transformational leadership suggests a role for its reinvention of the African higher education sector. Miano (2021) stresses the importance of transformational leadership in reforming universities to accommodate technological advancement and reorganize governance for efficiency and accountability, motivating the faculty and students to achieve high academic standards (Kiplangat, 2024).

Williams (2015) contends that quality education leadership, particularly in a globalized era with fierce competition, needs innovative leaders able to produce a range of policies and operations. We need leaders who are passionate and committed to educational success. Integrity is important in the leadership for Quality Improvement at moral level where integrity of quality management is important in providing the direction and vision. Values, goal setting, and directions for individuals in achieving macro and micro-goals are the central point of quality improvement (Ubaidillah et al., 2018). Education quality improvement is necessary because the building of strong educational systems require the commitment of all stakeholders at all levels of institution management – staff, teachers, administrators, students, for good results.

Statement of the Problem

African universities are commonly seen as important for the transformation of the individual and society. But a number of constraints to the expansion of higher education in Tanzania came out of findings of the study. These issues are such as non-adherence to international benchmark, embezzling of funds by administrators, lack of research experienced staff, overwork load, staff moonlighting and inadequate facilities such as library, ICT facilities and well-equipped laboratories. The difficulties in education are further confounded by the intricacies of daily practices and the ever-presentness of change. Therefore, when a university's culture is complex, and things have developed too fast, this shift of leadership perspective in the captain's quarters could do wonders for the health of our higher education system by spurring innovation. Leadership in HEIs should be transformative and dynamic in all components of an organisation as its efficacy is crucial to the

achievement of the institution. However, broad-minded leadership can have its shortfalls when it doesn't acknowledge the unique nature of the problems of the day. The purpose of the study is to examine the contribution of innovative leadership in promoting quality education transformation in higher learning institutions in Mwanza, Tanzania.

Research questions

One research question was formulated to guide the study:

1. To what extent does innovative leadership influence the transformation of quality education in higher institution in Mwanza, Tanzania

Empirical Literature Review

A number of empirical studies have been conducted to investigate the association of innovative leadership with transformation of quality education, providing some valuable inputs for this study. Wang and Ng (2022) carried out a research on “Transformational Leadership and Institutional Performance in Higher Education: A Study of Selected Universities in Singapore and Chinese”. The results indicated that the institution performance and enhancements in teaching and learning were largely driven by transformational and innovative leadership practices such as visionary thinking, promoting experimentation and inclusive decision-making. Nevertheless, although the investigation has shown a close connection between the innovative leadership and the educational performance, its Asian origins may pose a challenge when implementing it to Tanzanian organizations which may have unique cultural and governance issues.

In the Tanzanian higher education sector, Maro and Ngeze (2021) conducted a study on “Role of Leadership in Quality Assurance Practices in Tanzanian Higher Education”, which targeted all public and private universities based in Dodoma and Dar es Salaam. It was found that institutions had stronger quality assurance processes where there was creative leadership involved in technology embedded, staff development and participatory governance. These improvements were heavily associated with improved academic services and student outcomes. However, quality assurance was but one form of managerial hand that was privileged in the study and the leadership measures are relevant to educational innovation.

A regional perspective is presented by Alemu (2020) in “The Innovative Leadership Practices and Educational Reforms in Sub-Saharan African Universities” in Ethiopia and Kenya. Findings were qualitative and identified how pioneering leaders led change by fostering a climate of digitisation, distributed leadership, and flexible curricula. These actions significantly influenced the ability of the institutions to interact around academic agenda and build the research culture. The research provided in-depth insight into leadership innovation, but was small scale and there was no follow up data to explore the sustainability of the change.

The role of institutional leadership in digital transformation of Tanzanian Universities was investigated by Njau and Kimaro (2024). There was significant leadership innovation behind getting started serving digital platforms for teaching, administration, and students. These technology enhancements were correlated with increased academic productivity and understanding of student needs. Moreover, even when the study was limited to digital transformation, it was not full surveying of the other factors which have an impact on the quality of education such as the content of curriculum and academic research.

Leadership intervention studies have also been conducted in relation to leadership by Karanja and Wanjiru (2021) in their East African study “Leadership for Educational Transformation In East African Universities” conducted in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania which explored leadership practices. The study discovered even further-reaching effects on student retention, academic

collaboration and curriculum improvements in institutions with leaders who openly supported innovation and cooperation. However, the multinational nature of the study introduced noise to the conclusions as the study design, and with no quantitative data, the findings were diluted.

The above empirical results jointly verify that creative headmaster is the important factor for promoting the quality-education transformation. The promotion of digital tools, inclusive governance, responsive pedagogy and staff development are recurrent concerns in the studies. However, the majority of the existing research focused on innovative leadership as an independent variable and/or indirect study on institutions of higher learning within the Mwanza Region perspective. It is evident that this created a research gap that this current study aimed at bridging by evaluating the aspects of innovative leadership in transforming quality education in Mwanza, Tanzania.

Methods

The study adopted Mixed Research Approach. Hence, the approach offers the advantages of complementarily, breadth of understanding, and triangulation. It allows the researcher to gain deeper insights by exploring phenomena from different angles. Moreover, the quantitative approach was dominant in this study while qualitative approaches was less to improve comprehension of the study (Taherdoost, 2022)

Embedded sequential mixed research design (ESMRSD) was adopted in this study where the researcher went to the field twice, first collected information using questionnaire followed analyzed it then based on the quantitative information construct in depth interview guide visit the field for the second time phenomenology design was used to collect and analyze data on cultural dynamics of the specified research innovation as transformation tool for quality education. The design was preferred because is a two-phase mixed design in which quantitative data helped to explain qualitative results (Mgenda Mgenda, 2013; Creswell, 2014)

The population of study comprised of Heads of departments, deans, students who are studying in third year in higher institutions, hence the population was 400. Participants were full workers with a minimum service period of two year and above. This number of participants was considered sufficient to offer key information pertinent to the objectives of the study (Burke, 2011).

Probability sampling was employed in this study. A sample size of 150 from three higher learning institutions, categorized as follow: 40 heads of departments, 10 deans, 100 students who are studying in third year in higher leaning. Heads and deans and learners were stratified based on gender and simple random sampling was followed. These techniques allow the respondents to have equal chance of being selected or there is random collection of respondents for the research and each participant in the inhabitants had an identical and self-sufficient chance of being elected in the example (Burke, 2011). The researcher employs purposive selection to select ten participants out of 40 members in the population.

Questionnaires, in-depth interview guide as well as document analysis guide will be used to assemble information. Questionnaires will be used to collect information from lecturers and learners, while interview guide will be used to collect information from HLI's administrators. The researcher used questionnaires due to the fact that this kind of tool allows the researcher to gather information straight from the participants.

Instruments were exposed to the Department of research section and peer members in research furthermore, the academic staff questionnaire and students' questionnaire had an overall Cronbach alpha coefficient of $\alpha = 0.85$ correspondence, signifying that the instrument was reliable. Being a mixed research designs the researcher considered checking the trustworthiness of qualitative tools.

The use of phenomenology technique in data collection requires validation of interview and document analysis guides. (Mugenda, 2013; Creswell, 2014). It was done to show the clarity between the qualitative and quantitative study. Ethical consideration was observed

Table for results and findings

Means rating of the responses of the extent innovative leadership influence the transformation of quality education in higher institution in Mwanza, Tanzania,

Item	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	SD	Decision
Leader clearly articulated vision for the future inspires innovation	122	104	51	71	2.98	0.61	Accepted
I develop and communicate innovative strategies to achieve our goals	104	149	62	65	2.89	0.76	Accepted
I create a safe environment for my team to experiment and learn from failures	116	105	48	71	2.81	0.67	Accepted
I encourage my team to that a creativity and develop new ideas	146	147	50	78	2.96	0.68	Accepted
There is no foster culture of organization and collaboration	202	104	62	66	2.86	0.84	Accepted
The leader does not recognise and reviewed innovation contribution and behaviours	80	102	53	74	2.80	0.65	Accepted
I am flexible and adaptive to changing circumstances	103	150	60	66	2.92	0.86	Accepted
I am giving to new ideas and approaches	137	11	59	73	2.99	0.99	Accepted
I promise opportunities for my team to develop their skills and knowledge	153	100	51	77	3.00	0.83	Accepted
The leader does not seek and valued diverse perspectives and ideas	100	148	58	70	2.88	0.92	Accepted
Overall mean						2.92	

The means and standard deviation for the responses of lecturers on the innovation leadership the table reviewed that items were accepted in variation of means and standard deviation from items 1-10 to had means of above 2.50 and standard deviation between 0.61 and 0.19 which indicated that the responses presented were accepted as an indicated of the research questions been asked. The overall means of 2.92 indicated all the items were accepted. The finding was in agreement with Williams (2015) arguing that the power of educational leadership in the era of globalization with the dynamics of complex quality competition requires leaders who are innovative should be able to produce a variety of policies and operationalization of organizational work, has a passion and dedication to work, which is mandated to achieve the educational goals he leads.

Qualitative Analysis

Administrators known as innovative leaders are open to transformation as it is a determinant for quality education, heads of departments of various institutions in Mwanza clearly understand the leadership roles they play systematically, they develop, create a safety environment for learning, faster central organizational effectiveness and give new ideas and approaching to their subordinate, this is supported by Wang and Ng (2022) with study on transformational leadership and institutional performance in higher education. The result of the findings indicate that institutional performance and enhancement in teaching and learning were largely driven by transformational and innovative leadership practices such as visionary, thinking, promotion of experimentation and inclusive decision making. (HODS 5th August, 2025)

Conclusion

The study findings concluded that, lack of research experienced faculty, heavy teaching load, lack of moonlighting by faculties, and lack of resources such as library facilities, information and communication technology tools and non-well equipped laboratories influence quality in higher institution in Tanzania. Also innovative leadership is very crucial in the administrative functions of an innovative leader. The challenges of education are also laid upon complexity in daily norm and change as the only constant. For this reason, leadership must be delivered innovatively on every educational campus on a daily basis in order to adapt changes. Leaders change of view can help improve the quality of higher education system, through innovation.

Recommendation

The leadership that is provided to university should be innovative, strong and consistent at every level of organization. Since innovative leadership is crucial for the good performance of universities; the government of Tanzania and other stockholders should foster supportive system to lecturers for effective instructional delivery. Also innovative leadership should be provided in order to influence the transformation of quality education in higher institution in Mwanza, Tanzania.

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